

Does the Physicality of $(0, m_0 c c) \rightarrow (p, E)$ Imply Physicality of $(x, ct) \rightarrow (x', t')$? Part II

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In Part I, we noted how $m_0 c c$ and p, E were treated as physical attributes of a particle, but how x, t which represent a point on a trajectory (and hence a kind of x, t attribute at this point) becomes generalized to all possible x', t' values in $A = -Et' + px'$, a Lorentz invariant. In particular, p, E are assumed to be numbers (p a one dimensional vector) describing the particle, but any t', x' may be entered into the expression, including points not on the particle trajectory. This, we argue is important, because it leads to degenerate A values for $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$, ($n = \text{integer}$). We argued that if (p, E) are considered to be physical, then in some sense x, t should have a physicality to them as well. We argued that this physicality was the resolutions, \hbar/p and \hbar/E .

In this note, we wish to examine this matter in more detail by considering a photon. In this special case, the resolutions \hbar/p and \hbar/E actually define trajectory points in x, t . Thus, one may think of the resolution being described in terms of $1/p$ and $1/E$ or alternatively, E as $1/t_1$ and p as $1/x_1$, where t_1 is \hbar/E and x_1 is \hbar/p . This means that E and p , which are numbers, are somehow linked with a frequency and wavelength which implies periodic changes in space-time. To reconcile this, one may consider an energy and momentum density in both space and time. In such a case, E and p may be considered average values which is the standard way of treating a photon using electric field $= E \cos(-\omega t + kx)$ etc from Maxwell's equation. In other words, energy is no longer simply a number existing at a point (and a similar result for momentum density $1/\mu_0 E \times B$), but it is directly interlinked with intervals in space and time, i.e frequency and wavelength. Einstein's photoelectric work, however, showed that a photon is not spread out periodically in space, so this periodicity seems to be linked with probability, suggesting a quantum mechanical viewpoint.

In the case of the photon, one may go further, as we have discussed in previous notes, and argue that one should not only have gradations/resolutions for t and x in the direction of p , but also the sense of three space. In this case, unlike the rest mass one, one may create two perpendicular axes to the direction of p (which is in the x direction). One could then have a physical changing of the length of these axes in a periodic manner to create $E \cos(-\omega t + kx)$ y direction and $B \cos(-\omega t + kx)$ z direction. These are speculative statements here, but follow from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations as traditionally discussed in textbooks. In other words, the physicality of x, t in the sense of p and E dependent resolutions may actually appear in a energy and momentum density which is then linked to x, t as is the case of a photon. Thus, information is lost if one only thinks of E and p as numbers (p a 1-d vector) existing at a point. There is actually a physical manifestation of the periodicity linked with the resolutions \hbar/p , \hbar/E in the case of a photon.

E and p As Numbers/1 D Vector at a Point

In Part I, we argued that E, p (energy, momentum in one direction) are attributes for a particle, are represented by numbers and are considered to exist at each x, t . We then argued that if p, E which transform from $(0, m_0 c c)$ are physical attributes, that x', t' should also represent physical

attributes because this vector transforms from $(x=0,t)$ in the rest frame. Space-time may represent points on a particle's trajectory, but is usually not considered to be a physical attribute like E or p .

We argued, however, that given the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$, E and p are numbers pertaining to the particle, but x and t may take on any values because one may shift trajectories about. Thus, x and t represent a kind of two dimensional space containing all trajectories. In other words, one may have a specific trajectory in mind, but may use different x,t values for A . This is important because A is degenerate for:

$$x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E, \quad n = \text{integer} \quad ((1))$$

One cannot shift p and E about, these are specific numbers, but t and x in $A = -Et+px$ are not. Nevertheless, ((1)) shows x and t resolutions which depend on p and E which are specific physical attributes of the particle, and so in a sense, represent physical attributes themselves. Such a statement, however, is ambiguous and needs clarification. We try to do so by considering a photon.

The Case of a Photon

In the case of a photon, the special E,p resolutions ((1)) actually define $x-t$ trajectory points because: $A=0 = -Et+px$ and $E=pc$ in a vacuum. This is a special case, and one may consider alternatively that:

$$E = \hbar/t_1 \quad \text{and} \quad p = \hbar/x_1 \quad \text{where} \quad t_1 = \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad x_1 = \hbar/E \quad ((2))$$

Thus, in $A=0 = -Et+px$, one may incorporate a physical attribute linked to $1/$ time interval into E and $1/$ spatial interval into p . This is the traditional way of describing E and p for a photon, i.e E is related to frequency and p to wavelength. We argue, however, that the root of this are the degenerate points of $A = -Et+px$.

E and p for a photon, however, should be numbers, but if one has a frequency and wavelength, this suggests periodicity in x,t . To reconcile this problem, one may suggest an energy and momentum density. In such a case, E and p would only be average values over the periods \hbar/p and \hbar/E . Thus, E and p are no longer simply numbers at a point in a sense. Einstein's work on the photoelectric effect, however, showed that energy is not spread out periodically and so this density idea should really apply to probabilities. Nevertheless, it is E and p which are now linked with a physical resolution time and length.

To continue further, one might argue, as we have done in previous notes, that one does not only need to define a time resolution and an x resolution in the direction of photon motion, but that there should be the sense of 3-space. This suggests two perpendicular axes to x for the mo case. (This does not apply for the case of $m_0 > 0$ which is linked to the Dirac equation.) These axes could then change as $E \cos(-\omega t + px)$ y direction and $B \cos(-\omega t + px)$ z direction, with $E = B$ ($c=1$). This still should be a probabilistic situation because energy and momentum are not really spread out. An impulse p occurs at a point and all of p is present.

The point we wish to make is that only considering E and p as numbers leaves out too much information. There does in fact seem to be a physical time and spatial resolution linked to E and p which manifests itself directly in the 2-slit experiment. (This holds for both a photon and a particle with rest mass.) The case of the photon shows how this physical period and wavelength appear at least from the point of view of Maxwell's equations.

Maxwell's Equations as Quantum Mechanical Ones?

It is well-known that Electric field = $E \cos(-\omega t + px)$ (y direction) and magnetic field = $B \cos(-\omega t + px)$ z direction, $E=B$ ($c=1$) follow from Maxwell's equations with no charge or current densities. Classically, one would suggest that the electric and magnetic fields are changing in length, but given that:

$$\text{Energy density} = .5 \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B} \text{ and Momentum density} = 1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}, \quad ((3))$$

this would imply that energy momentum and energy are spread out over space contradicting Einstein's photoelectric effect work. (It would take too much time for an atom to absorb a photon.) Thus, it seems that ((3)) must already be associated with probabilities changing in x,t and so the exact physical mechanism for this still remains unknown.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part I, we argued that given that p,E transform from $0,, mocc,$ and are physical attributes, one should have some physicality linked with the identical transformation f $x=0, t$ to x',t' . We suggested that this physicality is linked to the resolutions \hbar/p and \hbar/E which depend on the physical attributes p,E . Here we try to extend these ideas to a photon because in this case, one may take the resolutions and apply them to E and p thus leading to a E and p being linked to a probability theory with periodicity in time and space. This theory seems to be that which is contained in Maxwell's equations.